

ISic1544

I.Sicily inscription 1544

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Agrigentum

Place of origin (modern)

Agrigento

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [ὁδεῖναΝ]εικάνδρου

2. [---ἔζησεν] ἔτη με

3. [--- υἱὸς] πατρί

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 493897

EDR 136089

EDCS 41300015

PHI 175594

PHI 330044

PHI 336056

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 49.1266.13

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Manganaro, G. 1999. *Sikelika: studi di antichità e di epigrafia della Sicilia greca*. Pisa, Roma. At 39 no.13 fig.90

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic1544. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4354378>